

Modelling, simulation & technique for harvesting solar energy

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Abstract

The paper discusses results of modelling and simulation studies undertaken on harvesting solar energy. Affordable and sustainable energy may force any nation's ability to advance economically and socially. India is a developing nation foresees its bright prospects towards rapid industrialization and urbanization, Which is further enhancing scope for application of new methods in search of continuously raising energy generating capacity. This paper presents a new method for cooling system for solar PV which results in the improvement in the collection of the solar insolation. The additional feature of the method has been the tracking of sunlight for efficient power generation. Further, the extra heat can be utilized for other purpose including heating and power generation through thermal means. The concept of the proposed system has been explained in detail with the pictorial representation. The validation of the improve performance of the proposed system, a detailed comparison with the conventional methods.

Keywords: Muslim women, slum, socioeconomic, poverty

Introduction

The utilization of photovoltaic structures, which convert solar radiation into a useful form of electricity, is a popular and extensively implemented renewable energy technology highlights the advantages of solar photovoltaic systems by lowering operating costs, providing little maintenance, having a positive effect on issue related to global warming, and having a higher power density than other non-conventional or renewable energy sources. In addition to the many benefits of photovoltaic technology, this energy conversion system has a few common issue that might negatively impact its performance, such as hail, dust deposition, and surface operating temperature. Exogenic climatic parameters, such as wind speed, ambient temperature, relative humidity, collected dust, and solar radiation, are the most frequent natural factors affecting a photovoltaic modules' s surface temperature. The efficiency of the PV module decreases by 0.4 to 0.5% for every 1 °C increase in surface temperature. As a result of the temperature rise, not all of the Solar energy that the photovoltaic cells absorb is transformed into electrical

energy. the remaining solar energy is transformed into heat in order to abide by the energy conversion law the overall conversion efficiency is decreased by the impact of this unnecessary heat. Different approaches to resolving this temperature issue that boost total conversion efficiency are needed to make renewable energy technologies feasible. The author provided a summary of various techniques for cooling solar cells in. But a closer inspection reveals that the work was limited to studying the passive. Different solar concentration system use forced air and forced liquid convection cooling techniques. Two cooling techniques that rely on active air cooling and closed – loop water cooling have been thoroughly examined and verified through experimentation.

Proposed system

The proposed solution for the cooling system with the tracking of sunlight. The PV system contains a PV cell that has at least one mirror attached to the PV cell. Two mirrors are included in the PV system. Each mirror is attached with a DC motor which is used for rotating the mirrors. The P

cell is attached to a heat exchanger, and fluid is circulated via a fluid pump and into a heat exchanger to cool down the fluid. Different components of the proposed system are described below:

The PV cell contains a sun tracking device that is configured to determine the angle and intensity of the incidence of the sunlight. The PV cell has a bottom surface configured to dispel heat produced by sunlight and photovoltaic cell operation. The mirrors may be a panel of reflective material that reflects solar radiation on the photovoltaic cell. The reflective material can reflect wavelength of ultraviolet, visible light and infrared radiation in the electromagnetic spectrum. The reflection of wavelength of 100 nm to 3000 nm can, for example, be specular, preferably 150 nm to 2500 nm, or 250 nm to 2000 nm. The mirrors are arranged above the top surface of the PV cell and are so large that the mirrors cover all or almost all of the surface of the PV cell when the mirrors rotate and lay flat. Each of the two mirrors is around one-half of the PV cell, and the mirror are disposed along the long edges of the PV cell. In an alternative way, the mirror can be arranged along the short edges of the PV cell, with less elongated, square shapes and each covering approximately one half the PV cell. In another version, the mirror can be

configured for further reflective panels to extend the reflective area. a spreadable mirror in one or more aspects of the subject matter disclosed. Via the hydraulic actuator and the DC motor, the mirror are connected to the PV Cell. The hydraulic actuators is fixed at a pre determined position on the side, for example, of the PV cell panels, at the first end. the DC motor is attached on the second end of the hydraulic actuators. the mirrors are attached to the center of the DC motor on the edge of the mirrors so that the DC motor can rotate the mirror clockwise or anticlockwise, or the two direction in which rotating switch after a predetermine period of time. the program for the rotational speed at a different rotation per minute (RPM), i.e less than 1RPM, 100 RPM or 5000 RPM. The hydraulic actuator can be set up to be extended or retracted by a quantity of fluid received or pumped out by the pump. This extension or retraction can increase or decrease the distance from the top of the PV cell from the mirrors. the mirrors can be connected via the hydraulic actuators and DC motors to the PV cell on each end. In an alternative way, the mirror can be connected to the PV cell by a hydraulic actuator and a DC motor and connected to the opposite end through a hydraulic actuator without a DC motor.

Fig 1: Proposed system [14].

Fig 2: Mirrors arrangements

Fig 3: Arrangement of hydraulic system

Fig 4: Different position of mirrors

Fig 5: Schematic diagram of the proposed technique

Performance analysis

Proposed System

As discussed in the previous section show the schematic diagram of the proposed technique for solar PV harvesting. The two mirrors A and B tracks the solar irradiation and reflects it perpendicular to the solar PV to get maximum energy. Due to the presence of the mirror, a shadow is created which is also

For the different formulation of the proposed technique. provides detailed information, where

m = mirror length (m)

C= length of the solar collector (m)
 θ = irradiance angle on mirror (radian)
 β = irradiance angle of solar (radian)
 Based on different length can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} X_1'' &= X - 1/2 M \cos \theta \\ X_1' &= Y_1 / \tan \beta \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

$$X_1 = \begin{cases} C - (X_1' + X_1'') & ; +Ve \\ 0 & ; -Ve \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} X_2'' &= X + 1/2 \cos \theta \\ X_2' &= Y_2 / \tan \beta \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

$$X_2 = \begin{cases} C - (X_2' + X_2'') & ; +Ve \\ 0 & ; -Ve \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Y_1 &= Y + 1/2 m \sin \theta \\ Y_2 &= Y - 1/2 m \sin \theta \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The shaded ratio (SR) can be calculated as

$$SR = (X_2 - X_1) / C \tag{6}$$

Therefore, the light ratio (LR) can be calculated as

$$LR = 1 - SR \tag{7}$$

The mirror angle θ based on the sun angle can be calculated as

$$\theta = (\beta + 90)/2 \tag{8}$$

Fig 6: Analysis of the proposed technique with one mirror

Fixed System

The main performance parameter for a collector is the collection of irradiance [15,16]. For collector, the irradiance I_c is calculated as [17].

$$I_c = I_{BC} + I_{DC} + I_{RC} \tag{9}$$

Where I_{BC}, I_{DC}, I_{RC} denotes the irradiance due to beam radiation, diffuse radiation and reflected radiation respectively. These three irradiances due to different radiations are calculated as

$$1. I_{BC} = I_B \times \cos\beta \cos(\theta_s - \theta_c) \sin\sum \square + \sin\beta \cos\sum \square \tag{10}$$

Where $\beta, \theta_s, \theta_c$ and $\sum \square$ represents altitude angle, solar azimuth, collector azimuth, and collector tilt, respectively.

$$2. \text{ The value of } I_B \text{ can be calculated as } I_B = A e^{-km} \tag{11}$$

Where A is the apparent extraterrestrials flux which is defined as

$$3. A = 1160 + 75 \sin[360/365 (n-275)] \tag{12}$$

While k is the optimal depth with expression given in eq (13).

$$4. S = 0.174 + 0.035 \sin[360/365 (n-100)] \tag{13}$$

Where n is the number of the day in the year
The diffused radiation can be calculated as

$$5. I_{DC} = I_B S (1 + \cos\sum \square / 2) \tag{14}$$

Where S is the sky diffuse factor which is calculated as

$$6. S = 0.95 + 0.04 \sin[360/365 (n-100)] \tag{15}$$

The reflected radiation for the fixed system is given as

$$I_{RC,F} = I_{BP} (s + \sin\beta) (1 - (\cos\sum \square) / 2) \tag{16}$$

PNS System

For the Polar axis North – South (PNS) System, the different are calculated with declination angle δ as

$$I_{BC} = I_B \cos\delta \tag{17}$$

$$I_{RC} = I_B S [(1 - \sin(\beta - \delta)) / 2] \tag{18}$$

$$I_{RC,NPS} = I_B \delta ((S + \sin\beta) [(1 - \sin(\beta - \delta)) / 2]) \tag{19}$$

From (7), (15) and (18), the isolation for new technology, $I_{RC,P}$ is given by

$$I_{RC,P} = I_{RC,F} \times LR + I_{RC,1-axis \text{ tracker}} \tag{20}$$

Results and Discussion

In order to show the improved performance of the proposed system. for the 1st day of January at 7:00 hrs. the isolation has a smaller value, however, the value of isolation is about 400W/m² for the 1st day of July at the same time. During the time period from 10:00-14:00, the level of isolation is about 800W/m². After 14:00 hrs. the isolation drops and at 17hrs, it reaches to a very low value. The peak isolation level with fixed system is achieved during the month of April and the isolation level is about 1000W/m² at 12hrs. Compare to the fixed system, the performance of the PNS system with 1-axis tracker is much better. The variation of the insolation with respect to the time for four different months with the PNS system, with the PNS system, the variation is low and from 9:00-15:00 hrs. the insolation level is about 800W/m². The peak insolation level with the PNS system is achieved during the month of April and October and insolation is about 1000W/m² at 12 hrs.

Fig. Shows the changes in insolation level with respect to the time for four different months with the proposed new technology. The insolation level of 1000W/m² is achieved for the month of April, July, and October from 8:00hrs to 16:00 hrs. further, the peak isolation level is about 2000W/m² which is almost double compare to the other two cases. Also, the proposed new technology gives a higher value of insolation for the all-time duration for all four months compared to the fixed and PNS system. The comparison of different techniques for the month of September has been depicted in fig. the proposed technology has a higher level of insolation compare to the other two methods of solar PV harvesting.

Similarly, fig. shows the performance of the three different technologies for solar harvesting different cities of India, and the proposed new technology gives improved performance in all cities for all months.

Conclusion

This paper proposed new technology for the solar photovoltaic harvesting method. In the proposed methods, the motor-operated adjustable mirrors are used for the improvement of the performance of the system. The performance of the proposed system has been validated through the theoretical analysis and the various comparison of the proposed system have been included in this paper which shows a better performance compare to the conventional systems. the major advantage of the proposed system has been observed in the collection of solar insolation which is two -fold compare to the conventional technique. however, during the of 11:00 to 13:00 PM, the reduction in the collected isolation is observed however this

lower value of isolation is still higher than the conversion fixed method. Also, the time duration for a higher amount of collected insolation has been improved.

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